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Research Article

**ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF UNRIPEN CARICA
PAPAYA LEAF SEED AND UNRIPEN FRUIT****Oshilim, A.O.**Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Delta State Polytechnic Ozoro, Delta State,
Nigeria**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

The study dealt with the antibacterial and anti-fungi activities of crude extract of leaves, seed, fruit of Carica papaya vari pus linn through agar well diffusion assay and poison plate assay against Staphylococcus aureus, Salmonella typhi, E. coli, Streptococcus, Shigella spp, Enterococcus spp. It was revealed that the crude extract of seed, leaf and fruit where effective to inhibit fungi pathogens while the crude extract of Carica papaya seed showed moderate inhibition of bacteria but leaf and fruit extract did not allow any inhibition against the bacteria. Many herbal remedies individually or in combination have been amended in various medical exposition in the cure of different disease medicinal plants represent a rich source of antimicrobial agents. Plants are used medicinally in different countries and are sources of many potent and powerful drugs, antimicrobial and anti fungi activity of Carica papaya plant different have extract is tested by methods reported in literatures.

Key words: Antimicrobial, Activity, Carica papaya, unripen, leaf seed

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INTRODUCTION:

A natural product is a substance produced by a living organism found in nature that usually has a biological or pharmacological activity for use in drug discovery and drug design. Natural products are important in the treatment of life, threatening conditions. Natural products may be obtained from extraction of tissues of plants, marine organism or from micro-organism fermentation. The search of newer sources of antibiotics is a global challenge pre-occupying research institution, pharmaceutical companies and academia, since many infectious agents are becoming resistant to synthetic drugs (Doughari *et al.*, 2007).

In recent years the growing demand to herbal product has led to a quantum jump in the volume of plant material. Hence the use and history of herbs are traced back to the time of the early man; they used herbs in their raw and cooked form to keep fit, since then the use of herbs has been known and accepted by all nations as the first act of treatment available to man (Bashra and Tajul, 2013). The active component of herbal remedies have the advantage of being combined with other substances that appear inactive (Ahmad, 2011). There is no plant that does to have a medicinal value, however parts known to contain the highest concentration are referred to therapeutic purposes and it can either be the leaves, stem, bark, roots, bulb, corms, flowers, seed or their fruits (Kafaru, 2008).

Sofowora (2011) and Baladrin (2015) defined medicinal plant as a plant in which one or more of the organs (parts) contains substances that can be used for therapeutic purposes of which the precursors for the manufacturing of drugs useful for disease therapy. The active component in these medicinal attributes are expected to be inimical to the growth of at least some micro-organisms especially the disease-causing ones such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Plasmodium species*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*. Much research has been done on the antimicrobial properties of much plant but for this study the leaf and the fruit of *Carica papaya* will be discussed.

Milind and Gurditta (2011) reported the medicinal application of carica papaya, the whole papaya including its leaves, seed, fruits and juice is used as a traditional medicine. The prominent medicinal properties of carica papaya include antifungal, antibacterial, wound-healing etc. This study is aimed at examining the antimicrobial properties of *Carica papaya* leaf, seed and unripen fruit on intestinal micro-organisms.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Sample Collection

Disease free young and green leaves and unripe fruit of the *Carica papaya* plant were collected from Imoniro otheremu street Ozoro community Delta State, they were washed and placed in a clean nylon and carried to the laboratory.

Collection of Tests Organism

The test organism that were used for this study were all human pathogenic culture organism which include *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella specie*, *Candida albicans*. they were collected randomly on sterile swab stick of faeces sample from 3 different individuals identified A, B, and C. each sample was inoculated into 12 sterile pour-plate nutrient agar and nutrient broth agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. They were then kept as stock culture in the refrigerator and 4°C for fungi they were inoculated into 3 plates of Sabouraud dextrose agar.

Preparation of Plant Materials

The samples of *Carica papaya* (leave, feed and fruit) were weighed on an electronic weigh balance and were blended with the aid of a sterile mortar and pestle the mixture were filtered with the aid of a Whatman filter paper to obtain a clear filtrate, the crude extract were collected into clean and beaker and stored in the refrigerator.

Sterilization of Apparatus

All glass wares and blending apparatus were washed with detergent and rinsed with distilled water properly. They were then air dried before wrapping in an aluminum foil and sterilized in hot air oven at 140°C for 2 hours. Prepared media such as nutrient agar, nutrient broth, citrate medium agar, TS1 agar were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes. Cork borer, glass rods and forceps were sterilized by flaming in Bunsen flame. The inoculating loop was also sterilized by heating in Bunsen flame to redness using naked flame before and after each use.

Identification of Organism

This is a test commonly used when trying to identify gram negative and gram-positive bacteria, this was done in accordance with the methods reported by (Cheese borough 2004)

Antimicrobial Analysis

Gram Stain Test

In gram stain test, gram positive bacteria retain crystal violet dye, while a counter stain added after the crystal violet safranin gives all gram stain is almost always the first step in the identification of a bacterial organism. Colonies were picked from the agar plate and smear were made on a clean slide with a loop full of normal saline on each side over flame several times the slide was flooded with crystal violet and allowed to stand for 60 seconds and rinsed

with clean water in order to decolorize it. The slide was flooded with lugos iodine for 60 seconds and rinsed with distilled clean water. The slide was flooded with excess alcohol and washed off after 30 seconds all flooded with safranin for 60 seconds after which excess dyes were rinsed with running water the slides were air dried and viewed under microscope using x 100 lens. Grams positive bacteria appear purple while gram negative bacteria appear pink or red.

Motility Test

This is done to test the ability of the organism to move. Nutrient agar was prepared and dispensed into different motility bottles based on the number or isolates the test tube containing the nutrient agar were placed on in a slant position until they solidify. Sterile inoculating needle were used to pick well isolated colonies and stabbed the slant medium to within 1cm of the bottom of the bottle and incubated at 37^oc for 24 hours. After the incubation of period, a turbid area growing away from the line of incubation indicates a positive result but no growth along the line of inoculation. It is regarded as being negative for this test.

Catalase Tests

This test detects the presence of catalase, which converts hydrogen peroxide to water and oxygen small inoculums were picked from the culture plate and placed on a clean glass slide and hydrogen peroxide was dropped on it. Immediate production of bubbles indicate positive result and those that do not produce bubbles are regarded as being negative for this test.

Oxidase Test

This test detect the presence of cytochrome C oxidase that is also to reduce oxygen an artificial electron acceptor. A filter paper was placed on a clean petri-dish and impregnated with 1% aqueous solution of nitrotetramethyl phenelindiamin-dihydrochloride then loop full inoculum from a pure culture plate was picked with a sterile wire loops the inoculum was smeared over the area of the filter paper containing oxidase reagent organisms that retain the purple coloration within five to ten seconds of the analysis were as being positive for the test while those that do not are regarded as being negative.

Citrate Test

The bacterial isolates were tested for their ability to utilize citrate as the sole carbon source, koser's citrate medium which different initiates the family enterobacteriaceae on the basis of citrate utilization the medium the medium was prepared and sterilized. After which it was dispensed into different test tubes and placed in a slant position until it solidifies it was inoculated at 37^oc for 24

hours. After incubation if the medium changes the blue colour with no growth it is regarded as being positive, but if it remains green with no growth it shows negative for citrate test.

Indole Tests

This test detects the production of indole from the amino acid tryptophan peptone water was prepared and dispensed into different test tubes after which it was sterilize allowed to cool and was isolated with a loop full of test organism and incubated at 37^oc for 48 hours. After the incubation period, three (3) drops of Kovac's reagent was added to each test tube and shaken. A red colour ring at the interface of the medium denotes a positive result but if not it is negative

Triple Sugar Ion (TST) Test.

Triple sugar ion (TSI) sugar contains lactose, sucrose, glucose, plus ferrous ammonium sulphate and sodium thiosulphate. TSI is used in the identification of enteric organism based on the ability to metabolize glucose, lactose, or sucrose and to liberate sulphides from ammonium sulphate or sodium thiosulphate. Acidic reactions turn media yellow. Basic reaction turn media orange. TSI agar was prepared, sterilized and dispensed into test tube and placed in a slant position until it solidified. Loop full of inoculum was inoculated into the medium and incubated for 24 hours. A blue dot colouration and production of a bubble to indicate gas production and crack in the medium indicate positive for this test but if no blue coloration and production of bubble indicates negatives for this test.

Antimicrobial Assay of Extract

The agar well method of the agar diffusion technique were used to determine the antibacterial activity of the plant extract. One millimeter of the different isolated organism were introduced separately into 30 millimeter of molten nutrient agar each in a sterile petri dish and allowed to set then labelled. A sterile 8mm glass rod was then used to punch holes (4 holes) into the inoculated agar and the agar was then removed three (3) wells that were formed were filled with the different concentration of the crude extract which were labeled accordingly, leave and seed the fourth (4) well contained a synthetic drug levofloxacin which served as a control drug, they were left on the bench for 1 hour for adequate diffusion of the extract and inoculated at 37^oc for 24 hours. After incubation the diameter of the zone of inhibition around the well were measured to the nearest millimeter along two axis i.e 90^oc to each other and the mean of the reading were then calculated.

The poison plate method was used to determine the antifungal activities of plant extract. Using plants

extracts and commonly used antibiotics (levofloxacin). The test quantities of specific extracts were dissolved in depending upon the solubility of the extract. The desolation of the organic extract were aided by water which did not affect the growth of micro-organism In accordance with control experiment. The surface of media were inoculated with fungi from a medium culture.

After 18 hours of incubation at the specific temperature of 28-30^oc the pates were examined and the diameters of the inhibition zones were measures to the nearest millimeter.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Result

This research work is self out to examine the microbial effect of unripen *Carica papaya* it takes a look at the comparative bacterial and fungal examination of different microorganism form stool sample.

This research study made use of micro-organism isolated form fence samples collected randomly form 3 different persons in Ozoro community the result show the bacterial isolated from the samples are *Streptococcus species*, *Staphylococcus auerus*, *Enterococcus, species*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella species* and fungi isolated are *Pnicillium species*, *Candida albican*, *Aspergillus species*.

From the result, table 1,2 shows the cultural morophological and biochemical characteristics of bacterial isolates and their heterotrophic plate count, table 3, 4 shows the number and percentage of occurrence of bacteria and fungi isolates. Table 5, 6 shows sensitivity of bacteria and fungi isolates table 5, 6 shows sensitivity of bacteria and fungi isolates to *Carica papaya* extract and possible zone of inhibition.

Table 1: cultural, morphological and biochemical identification of microorganism.

Sample code	Gram	Motility	Catalase	Citrate	Oixdase	Lactose	H2s	Gas	Acid	Indole	Organism
NA 11	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	<i>Streptococcus</i>
NA12	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	<i>E.coli</i>
NA11	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>E.coli</i>
NA12	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Salmonella</i>
NC 11	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Shigella</i>
NC 12	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Streptococcus</i>
BA 11	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>E.coli</i>
BA 12	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Salmonella</i>
BB11	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Streptococcus</i>
BB12	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus</i>
BC 11	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Staphylococcus</i>
BC 12	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>

Table 2: Bacterial/ isolates and heterotrophic plate count

NA 11	170	1.70 X 10 ²
NA12	1000	1.0 X 10 ³
NB 11	1400	1.4 10 ³
NB12	760	7.60 X 10 ²
NC 11	252	2.52 X 10 ²
NC12	140	1.4 X 10 ²
BA 11	250	2.50 X 10 ²
BA12	135	1.35 X 10 ²
BB 11	540	5.40 X 10 ²
BB12	200	2.00 X 10 ²
BC 11	127	1.27 X 10 ²
BC12	94	9.4 X 10 ¹

Table 3: Bacterial isolate , number and percentage of occurrence

Organism	Number of occurrence	Percentage of occurrence
<i>Staphylococcus sp</i>	2	16.7
<i>Samonella</i>	2	16.7
<i>Shigella</i>	1	8.3
<i>Streptococcus</i>	3	24
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	25
<i>Enterococcus</i>	1	8.3
Total	12	100

Table 4: fungi isolate number and percentage of occurrence

Organism	Number of occurrence	Percentage of occurrence
<i>Penicillium specie,</i>	6	40.0
<i>Candida albican,</i>	5	33.3
<i>Aspergillus specie</i>	4	26.7
Total	15	100

Table 5: Sensitivity Test

Zone of inhibition (mm) on bacteria isolates

Sample	Control (mm)	Pawpaw seed (mm)	Paw paw leaf (mm)	Paw paw fruit (mm)
NA 11	16	03	0	01
NA12	11	0	0	0
NB 11	12	0	0	0
NB12	13	0	0	0
NC 11	16	0	02	0
NC12	07	02	0	0
BA 11	15	0	0	01
BA12	17	0	0	0
BB 11	11	0	0	0
BB 12	18	0	0	0
BC 11	12	0	0	0
BC 12	15	01	0	0

Table 6: Zone of inhibition (mm)on fungi isolates

Sample	Control (mm)	Pawpaw seed (mm)	Paw paw leaf (mm)	Paw paw fruit (mm)
<i>Pencilium</i>	26	03	0.9	05
<i>Candida albican</i>	21	04	13	03
<i>Aspergillus sp</i>	22	04	10	06

DISCUSSION:

The result indicates that feces samples are loaded with pathogenic organisms that possesses harm to the environment and the human body. Table 5 shows 12 plates in disc diffusion and table 6 shows 3 plates in poison plate technique with bacteria and fungi isolates. It can be seen from table 1 that *Escherichia coli*: is a gram negative bacteria which ferments both glucose and lactose producing gas it is indole positive which indicates its ability to decompose the amino acids tryptophan to indole. Also *Shigella species* which is a gram negative organism has the ability to utilize citrate as its source of carbon. Glucose and lactose are fermented by *Shigella species*. Table 2,3,4 indicated that fungi isolates has the highest population compared to bacteria isolates in the feces samples. *Escherichia*

coli has the highest number of occurrence compared to *Entrococcus species* and *Penicillium species* has the highest number of occurrence compared to *Asperigillus species*

Antimicrobial Activity

from the result (table 5) indicated that crude extract of carica papaya seed showed moderate zone of inhibition of streptococcus specie in plate NA11 and NA12 and *Entrococcus spp*. In plate BC 12, extract concentration of *Carica papaya* leaf and fruit showed moderate zone of inhibition in plate NC11, NA11, and BB11.

In table 6, extract of *Carica papaya* leaf, seed and fruit showed more effective increasing zone of inhibition of *Pencilium spp* *Candida albican* and

Aspergillus spp with increasing leaf extract of it concentration of 5.10, 15mg/m.l the crude extract of the plant showed more effective result against fungi than bacteria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION:

Conclusion

This present study could however be concluded that the demonstration of antimicrobial activity against gram positive and gram-negative bacteria and fungi isolates is an indication that the plant is a potential source for production of drug with broad spectrum of activity. Non- standardized procedures of extract could lead to a degradation of the antimicrobial agents present in the plant and may lead to a variation, thus leading to the lack of accurate results.

The result supports the traditional application of the plant against human pathogenic organisms causing infectious diseases.

Recommendations

Carica papaya may be recommended as a useful source to prepare natural bioactive product from which we can develop new antimicrobial drugs which will be cost –effective because the plant is easily available and free in major areas of Africa, the plant extract possess compounds with antibacterial properties that can be used in their aqueous and crude extract state as antibacterial agents in novel drugs for treatment of gastro enteritis, urethritis, otiti media and wound infection. Further pharmacological evaluation and toxicological studies of possible isolation of therapeutic agents for drug design should involve screening of such various natural compounds and identification of active agents as a fruitful approach.

REFERENCES:

1. Ahmad I (2011) Antimicrobial And Photochemical Studies On 45 Indian Medicinal Plants Against Multi Drug Resistant Human Pathogens *J. Ethnopharmatherapeutic* 74: 87-91
2. Aravind, G Debjit, B Duravel S And Harish G. (2013) Traditional And Medicinal Uses Of *Carica papaya* . *Journal Of Medical Plant Studies* (1): 7-15
3. Bashra V And Tajul A.Y (2013) Papayo An Innovative Raw Materials For Food And Pharmaceutical Processing Industry. *Health Environmental Journal* 4(1): 68-75
4. Bladrin M.F, (2015) National Plant Chemicals: *Source Industrial And Medical A Materials Science* Pp: 228: 1154-1160
5. Iwu, M.W., Duncan, A.R And Okunji C.O (2008) Antimicrobial Of Plant Origin (Janick Edition) Perspectives Of New Crops And Now Uses ASHS Press.
6. Kafaru E. (2008) Immense Hup From Natives Workshop 1st Edition Elizabeth Kafaru, Lagos Nigeria Pp: 11-14
7. Milind P And Gurditta (2011) Basketfull Benefits Of Carica Papy IRJP 2(7) : 6: 12
8. Sofowora A (2011) Medicinal Plants And Traditional Medicine In West Africa 1st Edition Spectrum Books Ibadan In Association With Johnwilet And Sons London Pp. 204-208.
9. Udoh, P., Essein , J And Udoh , F (2005) . Effect Of Carica Papy (Pawpaw) Sad Extract On The Morphology Of Pituitary – Gonadal Axis Of Male Rat, *Phytother Res* 19: 1065-8